

Volume 9, Number 1, June, 2024

Geo-Studies Forum

An International Journal of Environmental & Policy Issues

*A Publication of the Department of Geography
and Environmental Management
University of Ilorin*

GEO-STUDIES FORUM

An International Journal of Environmental and Policy Issues

**Department of Geography and Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Sciences,
University of Ilorin, Nigeria**

ABOUT THE JOURNAL

Geo studies is a peer-reviewed journal, published by the Department of Geography and Environmental Management, University of Ilorin, Nigeria. The purpose of the journal is to make quickly available the fruits of Geography related researches with emphasis on the tropical environment. Contributions are therefore invited from any part of the broad field constituted by geographical or spatial sciences and studies in their economic, political, social and policy dimensions. Research may be broadly defined, but must be sound in methodology, critical, entertaining, analytical, make contribution to existing knowledge and conclusions drawn must address contemporary issues.

CALL FOR PAPERS

We cordially request the submission of original papers for possible inclusion in the forthcoming issue of GEO-STUDIES FORUM (ISSN 1596-4116), published by the Department of Geography and Environmental Management, University of Ilorin.

AREAS OF INTEREST

This scholarly peer-reviewed journal accepts original articles covering, but not limited to, the following areas:

- Geography
- Environmental Management
- Climate Science
- Soil Science
- Water Resources Management
- Biogeography
- Indigenous Knowledge System

- Urban and Regional Planning
- Transport Studies
- Demography
- Tourism Studies
- Geographic Information System (GIS)
- Disaster Risk Management

GUIDELINES FOR PAPER SUBMISSION

MANUSCRIPT PREPARATION

- Language: British English
- Format: Microsoft Word (MS)
- Paper Size: A4
- Font: Times New Roman
- Font Size: 12
- Line Spacing: Double
- Page Limit: 20 pages (excluding references)
- Abstract: Not more than 250 words, single-spaced
- Keywords: 4-5

MANUSCRIPT STRUCTURE

- Title
- Authors' names and affiliations (including emails of all authors, with the corresponding author clearly indicated)
- Abstract
- Introduction
- Methodology
- Findings
- Conclusion
- Recommendations

REFERENCES

- Format: APA
- Line Spacing: Single with hanging indent
- Space between references: 12 pt

SUBMISSION

- Submit to:
geostudiesforum@unilorin.edu.ng
- Include evidence of payment of nonrefundable assessment fee of ₦10,000 (Ten thousand Naira only)

PUBLICATION FEE

Upon acceptance, submit the reviewed manuscript with evidence of payment of a non-refundable fee of ₦20,000 (Twenty thousand Naira only)

BANK DETAILS

- **Account Name:** GEOSTUDIES FORUM
- **Account Number:** 2324256060
- **Bank:** UBA

CONTENTS

ASSESSMENT OF ADAPTIVE STRATEGIES EMPLOYED BY HERDERS IN THE PROVISION OF FODDER FOR LIVESTOCK IN THE GRAZING RESERVES OF NORTHEASTERN NIGERIA <i>Abubakar Hassan</i>	1 - 12
SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACTS OF WETLAND DEGRADATION: A REVIEW <i>Isaiah S. Akoteyon, Jimoh O. Saka, & Jolaade M. Olatunbosun</i>	13 - 38
ASSESSING INFLUENCE OF FLOODING ON SOIL TEXTURE IN AGWAN DODO IN GWAGWALADA AREA COUNCIL, ABUJA <i>Hadiza Abubakar Ahmad</i>	29 - 42
ASSESSMENT OF THE CAUSES AND STRATEGIES OF CONTROLLING SLUM DEVELOPMENT IN MARARABA, KARU LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, NASARAWA STATE, NIGERIA <i>Usman Abubakar Oseshi, A. I. Abdullahi, and I. Z. Ismail</i>	43 - 52
CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES IN MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT IN SHOMOLU LGA, LAGOS, NIGERIA <i>Grace Ometere Abu, Rayleigh Dada Abu, Esther Englama, and Henry Usiobaifo Agbebaku</i>	53 - 70
CLIMATIC VARIABILITY AND CHANGE IN THE HOLOCENE EPOCH IN WEST AFRICA: A DISCUSSION OF PALEOENVIRONMENTAL AND PALEOCLIMATIC CHANGES IN THE PAST 10,000 YEARS <i>TUBI, Paul-Kolade and OLATUNDE, Adewale</i>	71 - 81
DISTANCE – FROM –LEACH PIT AND QUALITY OF SHALLOW GROUNDWATER IN SELECTED WARDS OF ILORIN SOUTH LGA, ILORIN, NIGERIA <i>Balogun, Yekeen Idowu</i>	82 - 102
ASSESSING THE EFFECTS OF SPATIO-SEASONAL VARIATION OF CLIMATIC PATTERN ON AIR POLLUTANT CONCENTRATION IN JALINGO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, TARABA STATE, NIGERIA <i>Paulinus Ifeanyi Chukwu, Danjuma Ijudigal Garandi and Mohammed Sayd Dzarma</i>	103 - 115

EDITORIAL BOARD

- Dr I.O Orire:** orire.io@unilorin.edu.ng
08032942992
- Prof. L.T. Ajibade:** edabijalt@unilprin.edu.ng
08075251963
- Dr B.A. Usman:** usman.ba@unilorin.edu.ng
08036909201
- Dr Toluwalope M. Agaja:** agaja.tm@unilorin.edu.ng
07032329906
- Prof. Roda M. Olanrewaju:** lamoji@unilorin.edu.ng
08057674931
- Prof. Afolabi M. Tunde:** afolabi@unilorin.edu.ng
08038540145

EDITORIAL ADVISORY BOARD

- Prof. Gbadegesin, A. S. -** Dept. of Geography, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.
08033661346
adeniyig55@gmail.com
- Prof. Abdullahi, John -** Dept of Geography, University of Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria.
08036821438
drajohn74@gmail.com
- Prof. Ogunbodede, E. Funlayo -** Dept. of Geography & Planning Sciences, Adekunle Ajasin
University, Akungba, Ondo State.
08077860313
emmanuel.ogunbodede@aaua.edu.ng
- Prof. Akoteyon, I. S. -** Dept. of Environmental Management, Lagos State University,
Ojo, Lagos State. 08023161616
isaiah.akoteyon@lasu.edu

PATRON

- Prof. Adedayo, A. F. (Rtd.) -** Department of Geography & Environmental Management, Faculty of
Social Science, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.

JOURNAL'S CONTACTS

Address: Department of Geography & Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Science, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.

Emails: geostudiesforum@unilorin.edu.ng, edabijalt@unilorin.edu.ng

Website: Visit the journal website at: Geo-Studies Forum

CLIMATIC VARIABILITY AND CHANGE IN THE HOLOCENE EPOCH IN WEST AFRICA: A DISCUSSION OF PALEOENVIRONMENTAL AND PALEOCLIMATIC CHANGES IN THE PAST 10,000 YEARS

TUBI, Paul-Kolade, PhD

Department of Archaeology and Museum Studies, Federal University Lokoja

paul.tubi@fulokoja.edu.ng

&

OLATUNDE, Adewale, PhD

Department of Geography, Federal University Lokoja

adewale.olatunde@fulokoja.edu.ng

Abstract: *This paper examines the paleoenvironment and paleoclimatic variability and change of West Africa for the past 10,000 years. It makes critical attempts to retrieve, distill, and discuss relevant findings that give substantial clues to climatic changes in West Africa in the Holocene period. These findings are from multidisciplinary fields such as archaeology, geography, climatology, geology, history, botany amongst others. They point out incontrovertibly that the climate of West Africa has experienced changes in the past. Archaeological findings indicate strongly that the region has rich ecology and it is one of the world's most vulnerable regions to climate changes. The methodology of study engages in critical eclectic assemblage and review of diverse information, data and findings that shed light on the paleoenvironment of West Africa. The study unearths, distills, documents, and discusses the various aspects of the past ecology of the region. Research findings reveal that the study of climatic variability in West Africa provides sufficient findings on interconnectivity between human beings and environment. The conclusion from this study indicates that there are clear evidences of climatic changes in the study area and that these are in the archaeological, geographical, and geological records. The paper concluded that the past climatic variabilities and changes in West Africa give the region its present unique identity.*

Keyword: Archaeogeography, climate change, ecology, paleoenvironment, West Africa

INTRODUCTION

Climate is the statistical probability of the occurrence of various states of the atmosphere over a given region during a given period (Aremu, 2014). Thus, climate means not only the average atmospheric condition of a place over a period, usually between 30-35 years or more but also its extreme ranges, variability and the frequency of occurrence. Climate change on the other hand is a change in the state of the climate

identifiable by changes in the mean and/or the variability of its properties and persisting for an extended period - a decade or longer. It is thus a non-random change. It may be a result of natural internal processes or external, or to persistent anthropogenic changes in the composition of the atmosphere or in land use (IPCC, 2013; Nigeria Hydrological Services Agency, 2016). The amount and intensity of insolation, wind currents, ocean currents, and nature of ground

surface amongst others determines the climate of an area. These factors change through time. Some factors such as the distribution of heat within the oceans, atmospheric chemistry, and surface vegetation, change at very short timescales. Others, such as the position of continents and the location and height of mountain ranges, change over very long timescales. Therefore, climate, which result from the physical attributes, movement and motion of the atmosphere, varies at all known timescale.

As weather changes so too does climate although not as frequently, from changes in day-and-night cycles of the atmospheric conditions that result in specific weather to changes in total weather conditions in geologic time of hundreds of millions of years. Thus, in reality, climate is always changing. No two years, two decades, two centuries, or two millennia are exactly alike. Presently in West Africa, the variations of the wind system and insolation determine the climate. These variations result in a wet phase that is, characterized in the main by increased rainfall, which invariably leads to increase in the size of lakes, level of sea and green fields. The second phase being the harmattan / dry season characterized by dry soils and its degradation, as well decrease in the amount of water in lakes and river channels and fluvial actions, and also the formation of dunes coupled with wilting and dropping of leaves from deciduous trees, (Olatunde, 2013). This present climate from evidences was not the climate of the region in decades gone.

The evidences of the climatic changes of the past 200–300 years, especially since the early 1900s in most parts of the world, West Africa inclusive are recorded instrumentally and are in archives. Some of the very rare records date back

over 1,000 years. Researchers studying climatic changes predating the instrumental record rely increasingly on natural archives, which are biological or geologic processes that record some aspect of past climate. These natural archives, often known as proxy evidences are diverse and include, but are not limited to; fossils of past plant and animal distributions, sedimentary and geochemical indicators of former conditions of oceans and continents, and land surface features characteristic of past climates (Jackson, 2023). These evidences are parts of the two components of West African environment; physical (consists of rocks, landforms, soil, the ocean (Atlantic) rivers, coasts, lakes, and climate), and biotic (consist of plants and animals).

The Holocene in West Africa has been characterized by warm climate, massive population explosion, organised farming, domestication of animals, urbanization and technological revolution, (Andah, 1979; Sowunmi, 1981, 1985; Boboye and Akinmosin, 2018; Shanahan, 2018;) that provides further evidences of climate change in the past. Apart from these evidences, scholars like Dincauze (2000), James (2012), Lai and Dzombak (2019), Tomscha, Sutherland, Renard, et al. (2016), and Mesarovic, (2019), Zalasiewicz and Williams (2023), provide relevant discussions and strong evidences of paleoclimatic changes in general.

However, in particular, this article points to the fact that studies and available knowledge indicate multiple climatic changes in West Africa and that these changes are in the archaeological, geographical and geological records, (Oyelaran, 1993; Boboye and Akinmosin 2018, Frimpong, 2020; Shanahan 2018;). It posits further that; it is possible using multidimensional evidences to indicate climatic changes in West African and indeed all over the world.

Figure 1: Present Climatic Zones and Countries in West Africa
Source: World Meteorological Organisation (WMO) (2016)

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a qualitative approach to look at climatic variability and change in the Holocene Epoch in West Africa. It therefore used evidences, information and findings of archaeology, botany, geology, historical, climatology and hydrological amongst others of paleoenvironment changes and paleoclimatic variability in West Africa of various studies done earlier in books, journal articles and reports. It specifically reviewed literature pertinent to climate variability and change in the past. The focus of the literature search was on theoretical and empirical studies. Thus,

inferences were made with regard to the experience of other regions of the world where applicable.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

ARCHAEOLOGICAL FINDINGS: Archaeological data are important to understand the paleoclimatic condition of West Africa. The most important direct archaeological indicator is the discovery of the development of different types of tools implements or components that indicate changes in climate and human ability to adapt to those changes. Researchers discovered

climatic variability and change in their study of West Africa with archeological evidences that indicate climate change and large-scale paleoenvironmental trends. For instance, McIntosh and McIntosh (1981) explained the development of complex societies in the region as response to climate changes. In addition, McCann (1999) identifies climate as a major causation agent in African history.

These are well-documented facts in archaeological records. Archaeological data indicates that the intense development of agricultural strategies had widespread consequences on the ecology of West Africa (Chia and D'Andrea 2017). In the middle belt region of Nigeria, evidences have indicated changes in vegetation. In a major archaeological work carried in Iffe-Ijumu, around the Niger-Benue confluence area, Oyeleran (1993), substantiates paleoclimatic changes in the region and concludes that human impacts on the ecosystem was very intense which brought about change in vegetation from probably forest to the present Guinea savanna.

BOTANICAL FINDINGS: There are botanical indicators that support climatic variability and seasonality in West Africa. Scholars such as Sowunmi (1985), Hamilton and Taylor (1991) gave direct botanical evidences that indicate past environmental conditions in West Africa. Their studies of palynological evidences such as pollen analysis on offshore and onshore areas and geomorphological data of cores indicate a reduction of water in southern Guinea Savanna and rainforest vegetation at about 4,000 years BP. In addition, there are available botanical evidences, which further buttress the fact that there were important changes in the extent of the major vegetation zones of West Africa, in

sequence to changing climatic seasonality. Sowunmi's (1981) study revealed that there were shifts in the extent and dominance of the rain forest vis-à-vis the savanna. Data and finding indicate that the latter virtually came to replace the former because of its drastic reduction. From C. 7,600 BP- C. 2,800 BP there were evidences of fluctuations in the extent of fresh water swamp and rainforests on the one hand and those of drier savanna on the other. Some of these studies suggested that forests covered very large parts of the West Africa region several years and decades ago. This is indicative of alternating dry and wet climate seasons. It has resulted in the deduction that the rain forest faced remarkable reduction from C. 2,800 years BP in West Africa.

The migration of people from the Sahara Desert towards the coastal areas in West Africa has been related to the desert increasing dryness and aridity. This has resulted in the intensification and exploitation of some food resources such as yam and oil palm (Sowunmi 1985). In Senegal, the lower Casamance has sub-guinea vegetation with suggestions that the area once supported a dense forest consisting of large trees. Thus, the conclusion by scholars is that the forest once covered most of the areas of the lower Casamance to the Coast (Linares 1971). However, at present, small patch of areas are under reservation by the Government of Senegal.

ETHNOGRAPHIC FINDINGS: Through ethnographic study, scholars can infer climatic change as demonstrated by Greschke (2015), Johnson (2016) and Siltoe (2022). Ethnographic findings in West Africa point at deep and large forests that have now disappeared and water courses that have changed and vanished and of extinct animals. A good example being the study in 1978 among the Dutsen Kongba people of northern

Nigeria by the archaeologist York that revealed their village in their dialect being called 'Kitai Kongba', which when translated to English means "stone of banana-like plant". The 'stone banana plant or whatever it was, flourished on the outcrop and was successfully exploited by the people for brewing beer. Unfortunately, this plant has now become extinct, which could be due to over exploitation by human or of a change in the ecological conditions or both.

FINDINGS FROM ROCK ARTS: Rock arts are petroglyphs, meaning writings on rocks. Hemsing (2012) terms rock art a system of writing that documents aspects of peoples' lives and their environment. Klein (2022) stated that from rock arts, experts could explain climate change. Tubi (2021) in his study of rocks arts identified their usefulness in the reconstruction of paleoenvironment, and concluded that from similar studies by experts, there is lot of paleoclimatic information imprinted in images on rock surfaces. They provide useful data on paleoclimatic and paleoenvironmental conditions. The usefulness of rock arts in the study of past climate and environments has been emphasised across the globe.

Petroglyphs make meaningful contributions to our knowledge of the past, as there are increasing evidences for past climatic changes in West Africa. This fact is buttressed by the numerous rock arts that depicted several animals from the upper Paleolithic to Neolithic times. The faunas depicted on rock surfaces of the Sahara and Sahel regions can today be found in the moist and humid parts of Africa, West Africa inclusive. Paintings and depictions of elephant, rhinoceros, and hippopotamus on stone surfaces in the Sahara are at present found outside the area.

FINDINGS FROM DOMESTICATION AND ORGANIZED FARMING:

Researchers have made efforts to infer climatic seasonality by the understanding of the beginning of domestication and organized farming. Bakker (1976) connects the origin of agriculture in Africa to paleoclimatic change. Scholars point to the alluvial deposits noticed in the late Holocene at about 3,300 years BP; the deposits likely occurred in response to periods of meander migration and deforestation caused by human beings due to farming activities. Boboye and Akinmosin (2018) took this as a confirmation of climatic seasonality in West Africa.

In addition, archaeologists point at the invention of tools such as stone axes used for bush clearing and farming. Smith (1998) and Yasuda (2002) considered the origin of agriculture as evidence of environmental changes and human response to the emerging new environment. Furthermore, some scholars believe in the hypothesis that "a primitive centre of domestication" existed because of environmental change. They argued that the phenomenon of domestication was force on humankind by the evolution of the climate changing towards desiccation, (Chia and A'Andrea 2017).

GEOLOGICAL FINDINGS: Experts employ geological stratigraphy both in archaeology and in geology to indicate climatic changes of varying intensity and frequency in the past. In West Africa, such studies have indicated cycles of arid-humid-semi arid climates (Shanahan, 2018). Scholars like Adeonipekun et al (2017), and Miller et al (2016), amongst others argue that climatic change was a major factor that initiated today's identifiable geomorphological features in West Africa. They argued that the rejuvenation of streams related to the fall of Sea level induced by the drying climatic

phases. They concluded that the present rain forest area experienced periods of humidity alternating with periods characterized by extreme aridity in the period between 31,000 and 3,000 BP. Similarly, they opine that in West Africa, the wet periods reached their apex in c. 31,000-7,000 BP and 5,000-3000 years BP. The arid periods on the other hand reached their zenith c. 20,000-18,000 years BP and 7,000 BP. Andah (1971) however recognizes three geomorphological stable periods alternating with three non-stable periods, these stable periods, he claims correspond to the “wet”, “unstable”, and “drier” periods.

In addition, Laterites are surface soil formations from residual rock decay that are derive from weathering of igneous rocks. Scholars use laterite formations to explain paleoclimatic changes, especially the arid phases that occurred in the Guinea zone, because they formed when seasonal fluctuation of the water table occurred, especially under savanna or semi-arid types of climates and where aridity persisted for long periods that alternated with long periods of humidity. Thus, Thorne, Roberts, and Herrington (2012) argued that climate change is the major factor in the formation of laterites. In addition, Bonsor, MacDonald and Davies (2013), argued that there are clear evidences of laterite formation resulting from hydrologic activities.

HYDROLOGICAL

FINDINGS:

Hydrological evidences point to water resources in the past that give data on interconnectivity between humans and environment (Gasse, 2006; Jurgen, 2022). For example, some 5000 years ago, the Sahara Desert partly in West Africa now an arid area had numerous wetlands and lakes with shorelines occupied by human settlements (Hardy, 2003). Scholars like Andah (1979),

Burke, et al (1971), Gasee (2006), and Runge (2022), have utilized evidence of water resources to reconstruct the past. A classic datum in West Africa is the Lake Chad. The Lake Chad basin unmistakably points to a former humid condition than the present, especially in the area lying within the northeast Nigeria, which is shown by the strand lines of old lakes that are much larger than the present one (Andah 1979). The Chad basin has an inland Delta, which at the wet period saw a large lake formation in the basin, with water flowing over Bongor spillway, joining the Benue, but when it became dry, dunes formation occupied the floor.

At present under an intermediate condition, a lake without an outlet occupies the basin. In general, the Lake Chad once occupied an area of 120,000 sq. miles and was comparable therefore in shape and extent to the largest lake in the world today, the Caspian Sea. This evidence of such a gigantic paleolake in West Africa suggests a regional distribution of rainfall in the past than today.

In addition, in West Africa, hydrological information that scholars use to infer climatic variability and change in the past is the formation of the Bama and Ngelewa ridges. According to Andah (1979), at 40 ft. high running from Limani village in the Nigeria-Cameroon frontier to Yagoua, the Bama ridge is suggestive of an old shoreline of Lake Chad formed when the lake occupied an area of 80 miles. Bama ridge varies in length, in some places it measures as long as over 2 kilometers, while in other places, it extends just over few hundred meters. It has been arqued that sediments in the lakeshore were consequences of hydrological action and not wind. The Ngelewa ridge is lower than the Bama ridge, and its formation attributed to the same process

as that of the Bama ridge (Andah, 1979; Burke et al. 1971).

FINDINGS FROM DUNES FORMATION:

Dunes are sand mound formed by actions of wind in the desert or water-driven along coasts (Chase, 2009; Lacanster, 1995; Tsoar, 2013). Scholars contend that dune formations indicate paleoenvironment in West Africa and that system of dunes give some indication of the extension of arid condition south of the present limits of the Sahara, (Rendell, Clarke, Warren and Chappell, 2003). In Senegal, the mouth of the Senegal River indicates that during the time of low sea level, the lower Senegal valley was flooded by great dunes composed of sands flown from the desert. In western Sudan, it has been argued that, when conditions were very dry the Niger flowed only as far as swampy area of Timbuktu, making it possible for dunes to occur in the Sudan belt, (Munro, Ibrahim, Abuzied and E-Hassan, 2014).

Historical Climatological Findings: Historical climatology focuses on written sources that provided information on weather conditions. Historical climatology examines data from diverse sources like ship logs on wind movements, sailors' accounts of dykes' maintenance, agricultural records on crops, weather records, and archival records especially of missionary diaries, (Glaser, 1996; Kramer, 2006). Scholars like Norrgard (2014), Nash and Hannaford (2020) discussed the usefulness of historical sources as tools for paeloclimatic studies. They also point out how historical sources offer illumination of paleoclimatic variability and change in West Africa. A good example of this, come to us from ancient chronicles from Timbuktu, Bornu, Walat, Tichitt, and Lake Chad covering 1500-1800 AD. Travelers reported changing fortunes of the water during the 13th and 19th centuries. This gives an indication of abrupt change in the

weather condition of West Africa. Rainfall indices from recent centuries reveal that multi-decadal drought and dryness occurred and reoccurred thereby indicating that inter-annual rainfall variations are high in West Africa (Norrgard, 2017).

In addition, finding indicates that Lake Chad has shrunk 90 % over the last sixty years due to chronic drought and overutilization. Details from living memories give clues that severe drought from 1970s has shrunk the lake from 26,000 square kilometers in 1963 to 4,800 square kilometers in 2014 and 1,500 square kilometers currently (Baffour, 2020). Islamic scribes compiled stories that indicated that Lake Chad fluctuated in the last century (Burke et al., 1971). It appears that the Lake reached a higher level in the 19th century than the present especially in 1913-1915, and locals said that it experienced a low volume of water due to the severe drought of those years in the Sudan zone. The dryness of the Lake gave rise to speculations among local communities about inherent desiccation and the fear that the Sahara was advancing southward (Andah 1979).

However, scholars now assert that the lake is dwindling in volume of water considerably due to drier climate and decline in rainfall and it might go into extinction. In addition, sediments cores from Lake Bosumtwi in Ghana have so far provided very good evidences, as it concerns understanding precipitation patterns in recent centuries. These sediments cores reveal that there have been considerable changes in historical rainfall pattern, therefore West Africa may have been even drier than it is today (Norrgard, 2017). Historical sources that substantiate climatic change in the past in coastal parts of West Africa also come from early European travelers as noted in Portuguese

scrolls and missionaries' notebooks on weather, (Norrsgard, 2015).

HUMAN MIGRATIONS AND BANTU EXPANSIONS FINDINGS: Another evidence that indicate climatic change in West Africa is the recognizable fact of massive ancient human migrations in the area the iconic case being the expansion of the Bantu stock across the area to other parts of Africa. Bantu form the largest and the most widespread group of Niger-Congo language family. From their homeland within the Nigerian-Cameroon border, they flanged out to dominate other parts of Africa, south of the Equator, (Bostoen, 2018). The origin of the Bantu migration had been traced to early 3rd millennium BC in West Africa, when at that time deteriorating condition led them to move out of the Sahara to the Zairean and Sudan regions, in search of greener pastures thereby colonizing other lands, they migrated to. Cartright (2019) cites adverse environmental conditions as one of the main causes of their massive migration across Africa.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The discussion points out that there were marked evidences of climatic change in West Africa in the ongoing Holocene epoch. Archaeological, botanical, and geological records show consistently alternating weather conditions of arid-humid-semi arid phases from the past 10,000 years BP and even beyond. Ethnographic studies, history, domestication practices, Bantu expansion and tool technology invention support the presence of dynamic environmental conditions in West Africa that transpired in the past 10,000 years BP.

REFERENCES

- Adeonipekun, P. A, Adeniyi, T. A. Mateawo, J. and Agbalaya, B. (2017). The Late Quaternary Vegetational and Environmental History of Western Tropical Africa: The Eastern Benin Basin, Lagos Nigeria. *Geology, Geophysics and Environment*. Vol 43, No. 4. <https://journals.agh.edu.pl>
- Andah, B.W. (1979). The Quaternary of the Guinea Region of West Africa: An Assessment of the Geomorphic Evidence. *WAJA* (Special Book Issue), Vol. 9, pp 9-46..
- Aremu, J.K (2014) The Language of meteorology; Published by Cee Kay Bee printers Kaduna
- Bakker Van Zinderen, E. M (1976). Paleocological Background in Connection with the Origin of Agriculture in Africa. *Origin of African Plant Domestication*. <https://doi.org/10.1515/978311806373.43>
- Boboye, O. A. and Akinmosin, A. (2018). Palaeoclimatic Evidences from the Quaternary Coastal Deposits, Southwestern, Nigeria. *Open Journal of Geology*. Vol. 8, No. 6, pp. 585-605 doi:10.4236/ojg.2018.86034.
- Bonsor, H.C, MacDonald, A. M and Davies J. (2014). Evidence of Extreme Variations in the Permeability of Laterite from a Detailed Analysis of Well Behaviour in Nigeria. *Hydrological Processes* 28 (10), pp. 3563-3573, DOI:10.1002/hyp.9871
- Bostoen, K. (2018). The Bantu Expansion. DOI:10.1093.acrefore/9780190277734.013.19.

Burke et al. (1971). A Dry Phase of the Sahara 20,000 Years Ago. *West African Journal of Archaeology*, 1: Pp. 1-8.

Cartright, M. 2019. Bantu Migration. *World History Encyclopedia*. Retrieved from https://www.worldhistory.org/Bantu_Migration

Cerasoni, M. K, Hallet, E. Y, Arous, E. B, Beyer, R. M, Krapp, M, Manica, A, Scerri, E. M, (2022). Archaeological Sites and palaeoenvironments of Pleistocene West Africa. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17445647.2022.2052767>

Chase, B. (2009). Evaluating the Use of Dune Sediments as a Proof for Paleo-Aridity: a Southern Africa Case Study. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 93, pp. 31-45.

Chia. R and A'Andrea A. C. (2017). Food Production in the Forest Zone of West Africa:

Archaeological and Historical Perspectives. *African History*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190277734.013.139>.

Dincauze, D. F. (2000). *Environmental Archaeology: Principles and Practices*. Cambridge: Cambridge University press.

Frimpong, O. B (2020). Climate Change and Fragility in the Lake Chad Basin. <https://africaupclose.wilssoncenter.org>

Gasse, F. (2006). Climate and Hydrological Changes in Tropical Africa During the Past Million Years. *Comptes Rendus Palevol*, Volume 5, Issues 1-2, pp 35-43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crpv.2005.09.012>

Greschke, H. (2015). The Social Facts of Climate Change: An Ethnographic Approach. In Greschke, Heike, Tischler, Julia (eds)

Grounding Global Climate Change Dordrecht; Springer, pp. 121-138.

Hamilton, A. C and Taylor, D (1991). History of Climate and Forests in Tropical Africa During the Last 8 Million Years. *Climate Change*, Volume 19, pp 65-78, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00142215>.

Hardy, J.T (2003). *Climate Changes-Causes, Effects and Solutions*. John Wiley and Sons Chichester, England.

Hemasing, K. (2012). The Importance of Petroglyphs. <https://blogs.ubc.ca>

Herton, R. (1979). Ancient Ife: A Reassessment. *Journal of Historical Society of Nigeria*. 9(4). <https://drum.lib.umd.edu> University of Maryland: DRUM.

James, B. (2012). Recent Themes in the Environmental History of the British Empire. *History Compass*. 10 (2), pp 129-139. Doi:10.1111/j.1478-0542.2011.00824.x

Johnson, K. J. (2016). Resilience to Climate Change: An Ethnographic Approach. *Journal of Biogeography*. Vol. 8, No. 6, 457-477.

Juergen, J. G. (2022). Paleoenvironment and Hydrological Characteristics of the Eastern Congo Basin, Central Africa. *Authorea*. DOI:10.1002/essoar.10500749.1

Klein, A. (2022). Ancient Aboriginal Rock Art May Reveal How Australia's Climate Changed. *New Scientist*. <https://www.newscientists.com>

Lai. Y and Dzombak. D (2019). Use of Historical Data to Assess Regional Climate Change. *Journal of Climate*, 32(14), DOI:10.1175/JCLI-D-18-0630.1)

- Lancaster, N. (1995). The Geomorphology of Desert Dunes. London and New York: Routledge. Man, Royal Anthropological Institute of Great Britain, Vol. 6, No. 3, pp. 493-495.
- Mesarovic, M. (2019). Global Warning and other Climate Change Phenomena on the Geological Time Scale. *Thermal Science* 23(00), DOI:10.2298/TSCI190208320
- McCann, J. C. (1999). Climate and Causation in Africa History. *The International Journal of African Historical Studies*. Vol. 32, No. 2/3, pp. 261-279. Boston University African Studies Center. <https://doi.org/10.2307/220342>
- McIntosh, S. K and McIntosh, R. S (1981). West African Prehistory. *American Scientist* 69.6, pp 602-613.
- Miller, C. S, Gosling. W. D. Kemp, D. B, Coe, A. L and Gilmour, I. (2016). Drivers of Ecosystem and Climate Change in Tropical West Africa Over the Past 540,000 Years. *Journal of Quaternary Science*, Volume 31, Issue 7, pp. 671-677. <https://doi.org/10.10002/jqs.2893>.
- Munro, R. N, Ibrahim, M. A. M, Auzied, H, El-Hassan, B, (2014). Aeolian Sand Landforms in Parts of the Sudan and Nubia. Origins and Impacts on the Past and Present. *The Sudan Archaeological Research Society*, no 16. <https://ISSUU.COM>
- Nash, D and Hannaford, M. (2020). Historical Climatology in Africa: A State of the Art. *Past Global Changes Magazine*, 28(2), pp. 42-43. <https://doi.org.10.22498/pages, 28.2.42>
- Nickel laterites. *Geology*, 40(4), pp 331-334 DOI:10. 1130/G32549.1)
- Nigeria Hydrological Services Agency (2016) Glossary. Annual Flood Outlook, Federal Ministry of Water Resources July.
- Norrgard, S. (2015). Practising Historical Climatology in West Africa: a Climate Periodisation 1750-18000. *Climate Change* 129 (1-2), pp. 131-143. DOI:10.10007/s10584-014-1307-9.
- Norrgard, S. (2017). Changes in Precipitation over West Africa During Recent Centuries. Oxford Research Encyclopedia. *Climate Change*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190228620.013.536>
- Oguntoyinbo et al. (1973). Rainfall, Drought and Food Supply in South-Western Nigeria. *Savanna* 2(2): 115-120.
- Olatunde, A.F. (2013) Analysis of Drought Occurrences in Northern Nigeria: Implications for Agricultural Planning and Development, Ph.D. Dissertation, Department of Geography, Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna.
- Olga Linares (1971). Shell Middens of Lower Casamance and Problems of Diola Protohistory. *WAJA* Vol. 1: 23-54.
- Oyelaran, P.A. (1993). A Preliminary Report on Palaeoenvironmental Investigations in Iffe-Ijumu, Permeability of Laterite from a Detailed Analysis of Well Behavior in Nigeria. *Hydrological Processes* Volume 28, Issue 10, pp. 3563-3573,
- Rendell, H. M, Clarke, M. L. Warren, A. and Chappell, A. (2003). The Timing of Climbing Dune Formation in Southwestern Niger: Fluvio-Aeolian Interactions and the Role of Sand Supply. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, Vol. 22, Issues 10-13, pp. 1059-1065. <https://doi.org/10.101016/S0277-X>

- Shanahan, T. M. (2018). Quaternary Climate Variation in West Africa. *Climate Science* <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190228620.013.526>
- Shaw, T, (1963). Field Research in Nigerian Archaeology. *Journal of Historical Society Nigeria*. Vol 2, Issue 4.
- Shaw, T. (1964). *Archaeology and Nigeria*. Ibadan: University. Press.
- Shaw, T. (1970). Igbo-Ukwu: An Account of Archaeological Discoveries in Eastern Nigeria.
- Silitoe, P. (2022). *The Anthropocene of Weather and Climate: Ethnographic Contributions to the Climate Change Debate*, Berghahn Books
- Smith. B. D. (1998). The Emergence of Agriculture. New York: Scientific American Lib.
- Southwestern Nigeria, Papers from the Institute of Archaeology, University College London. 4, pp. 1-8 doi:<https://doi.org/10.5334/pia.50>.
- Sowunmi, M.A. (1981). Aspects of Late Quaternary Vegetational Changes in West Africa. *Journal of Biogeography*. Vol. 8, No. 6, Pp. 457-477
- Sowunmi, M.A. (1985). The beginnings of Agriculture in West Africa: botanical-evidence. *Current anthropology* 26(1): Pp.127-129.
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (2013). Annex III: Glossary. In Planton, S.(Ed). *Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment*
- Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change Jackson, Stephen T. (2023)
- Climate Change. *Encyclopedia Britannica*, 30 Jul.2023,<https://www.britannica.com/science/climate-change>. Accessed 31 July 2023.
- Thorne, R., Roberts, S. and Herrington, R. J. (2012). Climate Change and the Formation of Nickel Laterite Deposits. *Geology* 40 (4) 331-334. <https://doi.org/10.1130/G32549.1>
- Tomscha, S. Sutherland, I. J. Renard, D, et al. (2016). A Guide to Historical Data Sets for Reconstructing Ecosystem Service Change over Time., *Bioscience*, Volume 66, Issue 9, Pp. 747-762.
- Tsoar, H. (2013). Critical Environments: Sand Dunes and Climate Change. In John F. Shroeder (ed) *Treatise on Geomorphology, Vol 11: Aeolian Geomorphology*. San Diego.:Academic Press, pp. 414-427.
- Tubi, P-K (2021). Archaeology of Rocks and the Relevance of Petroglyphs in the Reconstruction of History: An Outline form Valcamonica, Italy. *SGOJAHDS* vol 4, No 4, pp. 215-224. www.sgojahds.com
- United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change UNFCCC). (<https://unfccc.int>).
- World Meteorological Organization. (2016). *WMO statement on the status of the global climate in 2015*. World Meteorological Organization (WMO).
- Yasuda, Y. (2002). *The Origin of Agriculture*. New Delhi: Roli Books Ltd
- York, R.N. (1978). Excavations at Dutsen Kongba, Plateau State, Nigeria. *WAJA* 8, 138-163.
- Zalasiewicz J. and Willimas. M. (2023). *Geological History of Climate* <https://www.climate-policy-watcher.org>